

DATA COLLECTION SYSTEM IN THE MANAGEMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES

Ismanov Muhammadziyo

PhD of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology

e-mail: ismanovm91@gmail.com

Mirzaikromov Xamidilloxon

Magistr of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology

Annotation: *The OPC server can be integrated with all currently available programmable logic controllers. Forms and transmits protocols in accordance with the international standards used in them. MasterOPC has two OPC interfaces that highlight keywords, work easily with tags and libraries. Created documentation on the development of their own protocols - for example, DCON, Rnet, scalable Modbus, as well as the ability to work with archives.*

Keywords: *OPC server, Master OPC, DCON, Rnet, Modbus, Simp light SCADA, TCP Server, Lokal, WEB-brauzer.*

Introduction

It is necessary to develop the integration of the created technical devices and programs, the development of the user interface in the development of a whole system. Modbus universal MasterOPC Server combines the capabilities of an OPC server over the Modbus RTU/ASCII/TCP broadcast protocol, as well as tools for the development of new OPC servers, including support for Modbus extensions and other protocols.

MasterOPC implements two OPC interfaces - DA (Data Access - current data) and HDA (Historical Data Access - archive data) interfaces. Master OPC uses SQL or Mysql server to organize storage of requested variable archives.

The OPC server supports a simple programming language. This allows them to pre-process data before reading it from external devices or to process it

after it is written. There are options for using scripts to write new drivers (for protocols built into Modbus transport, as well as others), saving archives on SQL server, recording signals through simulators, calculating indirect parameters, and more. Scenarios can be used at the level of communication nodes, devices and ost devices, individual tags.

Server editor provides standard services - highlights keywords, works easily with tags and libraries. Added documentation on developing own protocols - eg DCON, Rnet, extensible Modbus, as well as options for working with archives.

Programming language capabilities:

- Access to predefined keywords and built-in function editor, tags and libraries;
- Minimize and maximize code in the editor
- Simple ways of working on OPC DA and HDA servers for any communication protocols;
- Working with quality indicators;
- Ability to work with simulation devices when devices are not available (using script);
- Data archiving in SQL Lite.

Experiments and results.

OPC server connection with DMK should be restored. To get information to the OPC server, the following actions are performed. After starting the server, select the item "Communication node" from the "Dabavit" section of the "Server" menu. The name of the network is entered in the "Node name" section (Modbus RTU). Select the item "com" from the "Disconnect Type" section. As a result, the port number and data transfer speed are entered for the connection (9600 baud/second). The address of the DMK is entered in the node section (the address of the controller is taken as 16 in the program). Other settings may be default. We enter the address of the device, after which we declare tags (variables) at address

16 of the DMK. These variables are determined from a program written using CodeSys software. Register addresses of DMK network variables must be specified on the OPC server (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. DMK and OPC server integration.

Above, using the Modbus RTU protocol, the values of the variables coming from the DMK platform were connected to the OPC server. Using these values, it was possible to interface with the Simp Light Scada system. Integrated with Master OPC Universal Modbus server with DMK platform. The advantage of this system is to collect data on one server and to transfer, receive and process data using any protocol, as well as to archive data and ensure integration with SQL servers.

In order to create an interface in the Simp Light scada system, it is necessary to work seamlessly with the OPC server.

Today, there are various SCADA systems in the market of automated control systems. Functional parameters of all systems are the same. In most cases, they are selected based on large and medium-sized automated facilities. For small dispatch systems, such systems are unnecessary, difficult to learn and understand.

The SIMP Light system provides all the main features of a SCADA system:

- permanent collection of primary information from low-level devices

(controlling devices, data collection devices) using OPC servers;

- data storage on the hard disk of the computer in the database;
- development of mnemonic schemes of the process;
- display of received data in digital and graphical form on the interface;
- reporting accidents, recording accidents in the journal, monitoring confirmation of messages;
- perform mathematical operations on data;
- export data from the database to Excel and other programs in CSV, XLS formats;
- built-in WEB server (allows you to view the measured values using IE, Opera, Firefox, etc. on any computer connected to the network);
- organization of a multi-user system.

The SIMP Light system architecture can be seen in two parts:

- Network architecture. Depending on the version, SIMP Light can work in local or network modes.

In local mode, with SIMP Light installed on the computer, the instruments are connected and the process is monitored from this computer. Data can be viewed graphically at the process data collection station, as well as tabular data from any computer connected to the computer network through a WEB browser. To implement this scheme, you must have a license, only on a computer with SIMP Light installed, the WEB client access license is not required (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Simple light SCADA local architecture.

A complex and flexible architecture can be organized according to the network architecture. In SIMP Light SCADA server mode, devices are installed on the connected computer, in client mode, SIMP Light is installed on other PCs in the network. A special feature of this mode is that SIMP Lightning allows all network clients to display the same interfaces as the data collection station (Figure 3).

Figure 2. SImp light SCADA server architecture.

Component architecture.

Evaluation.

The SIMP Light software package consists of four interrelated blocks:

- Module Editor channel. In this module, the signal parameters from the channel are filled (activity, maximum and minimum measurement, signal settings, channel name, polling interval, etc.);
- Module Editor mnemonic. This module helps the user with a tool that allows you to configure the mnemonic schemes of the technological process without the participation of a software tool;
- Module Monitor. This module receives data from devices, processes it, archives it, and manages input data to detect out-of-range settings. Displays incoming information in text (as a table or advanced diagram) and graphically (trends);
- Modul Prosmotrshchik - allows you to see the value of technological indicators in the database in graphic and text form, print and export databases in Excel or CSV format.

SIMP Light program features:

Driver:

- Modbus driver TCP / RTU (network and COM port);
- OPC DA (working with current data);
- OPC HDA (working with archived data);
- Modbus Slave TCP;
- Free programmable HTTP/S.

Warning system:

- Notifications in the mnemonic diagram;
- Voice notification;
- EMAIL alerts;
- SMS notification;
- Alarm and event log;

- Alerts in Telegram.

Integration:

- Modbus slave (as SCADA controller);
- SQL ODBC support;
- Interaction through HTTP / S;
- Text files.

Data storage system:

- Reliable database;
- Repetitive storage of information to databases (MSSQL, mySQL);
- Access to data from scripts;
- No archiving limit.

Conclusion

1. The OPC server supports a simple programming language. This allowed them to pre-process data before reading it from external devices or to process it after it was written.

2. "Communication node" item was taken from the "Dabavit" section of the "Server" menu to get information to the OPC server.

3. The main components of the SCADA system: remote terminal RTU - free central terminal (MTU) - communication channel or communication system, as well as (CS) principles and tasks are presented.

4. SCADA system was created using OPC server and Simp Light Scada software.

REFERENCES

1. Ismonovich K. A., Abdusamatugli I. M. Modeling the Method of Linear Approximation of Signals in SPLC (Sensor Programmable Logic Controller) //International Journal on Orange Technologies. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 10. – C. 55-59.

2. Ismonovich K. A., Muhammadziyo I. Mathematical Modeling of Heat Flux Distribution in Raw Cotton Stored in Bunt //Engineering. – 2020. – T. 12. – №. 8. – C. 591-599.
3. Mardonov B., Tadaeva Y., Muhammadziyo I. Experimental and theoretical studies of vibrational motion of raw cotton on inclined mesh surface //International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research. – 2014. – T. 9. – C. 78-85.
4. Muhammadziyo I. Research Of Characteristics And Analysis Of Calculations Of Optoelectronic Hydrometers Of Automatic Control //Solid State Technology. – 2020. – T. 63. – №. 6. – C. 14910-14916.